

Interactions Between Robot Personality and Perceived Empathy: A Comparative Study on Nao and Pepper Robots

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Abstract—As robots become increasingly integrated into our daily lives, their ability to connect with humans on an emotional level is of paramount importance. This proposed research delves into the intricate dynamics of robot personality traits, their appearance, and the resultant perceived empathy during human-robot interactions. Drawing on the novelty of merging these areas of study, we aim to explore how specific personality traits, combined with robot appearance, influence human perceptions of robot empathy. By leveraging both Nao and Pepper robots, we intend to add an additional layer of comparison through appearance variations. Our objective is to inform robot design practices, optimize empathetic human-robot interactions, and provide substantial contributions to the broader discourse on robotic design and human-robot interaction.

Index Terms—Human-Robot Interaction, Social Robotics, Robot Personality, Empathy

I. INTRODUCTION

As we progressively integrate robots into various facets of our daily lives, their ability to interact socially with humans has become paramount. While technical competencies, efficiency, and task accuracy remain essential, the social dynamics between humans and robots are rapidly emerging as a critical research domain. Among the myriad of factors influencing human-robot interaction (HRI), two standout elements are the robot's perceived personality and its capability to exhibit empathy. Recently, social robots emerge in many areas. This has led to the development of research on such robots. This work seeks to delve deeper into the confluence of these aspects, exploring how they together shape the qualitative aspects of HRI.

II. BACKGROUND

A. *Theory of Mind*

Fundamental to human interactions, Theory of Mind (ToM) refers to the cognitive ability to recognize and attribute mental states—such as beliefs, intents, desires, and emotions—to oneself and others. It serves as the foundation for empathy, enabling one to understand that others might have feelings and perspectives distinct from their own. In the realm of robotics, instilling a form of ToM can be pivotal. It not only enables

robots to better predict and comprehend human emotions but also facilitates more nuanced and empathetic interactions.

B. *Empathy*

Empathy, described as the capability of a robot to recognize and appropriately respond to a human's emotional state, thoughts, and circumstances, is pivotal for robots designed for intimate settings like homes or service areas such as airports. An extensive review by Park, S et al [1] emphasized the significance of empathy in human-robot interactions (HRI) and presented a comprehensive framework detailing the key components necessary when designing an empathic robot. This review highlighted the importance of domain specificity, multimodality, and the modulation of empathy for the optimal functioning of social robots. Recent studies have started to explore the perception of empathetic expressions by robots. For instance, Birmingham et al delved into how viewers perceive different forms of empathetic expression by robots, focusing on cognitive and affective empathetic responses [2]. More recently, Charrier et al. [3] introduced the Robot's Perceived Empathy (RoPE) scale to provide a means of directly measuring the perceived empathy of a robot. This scale provides a measure of the second person perspective of the robot.

C. *Robot Personality*

In the realm of social robotics, personality is more than just a set of static characteristics. It dictates the robot's behavior, communicative style, responsiveness, and even its non-verbal cues. Previous research has showcased that robots endowed with certain personalities can lead to more effective and engaging interactions with humans. For instance, robots portraying extroverted characteristics may be better received in lively settings, whereas those with introverted traits might excel in calm, one-on-one interactions.

D. *Perceived Empathy*

Empathy, the ability to understand and share the feelings of another, has long been considered a uniquely human trait.

In the context of HRI, perceived empathy doesn't mean the robot genuinely feels or understands emotions, but rather its ability to exhibit behaviors that make it seem empathetic to the human user. Research suggests that robots that exhibit signs of empathy, whether cognitive or affective, tend to foster trust, promote user engagement, and enhance overall interaction quality.

A notable exploration into perceived empathy in dialogue systems revolves around the role of "shared laughter". Research has shown that systems which recognize and respond to a user's laughter are perceived as more empathetic than those without such capabilities. This underscores the importance of nuanced interactions, like laughter, in shaping human perceptions of empathy in conversational agents [4]. This insight suggests further avenues for exploration in our study on robot personality and perceived empathy.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS

A. Objectives

To investigate how the designed personalities (extroverted vs. introverted and assertive vs. passive) of humanoid robots (Nao and Pepper) influence human perceptions of their empathetic abilities.

B. Research Question

How does a robot's designed personality (extroverted vs. introverted, assertive vs. passive) influence its perceived empathy?

IV. METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW

A. The Robots

a) *Nao*: Nao is an autonomous, programmable humanoid robot developed by Aldebaran Robotics in 2008. Its height is 574 millimetres and weight is approximately 5 kilograms. Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Nao robot.

b) *Pepper*: Pepper is a semi-humanoid robot manufactured by SoftBank Robotics. It is designed with the ability to read emotions. Fig. 2

Fig. 2. Pepper robot.

B. Robot Personality Design

We will design and implement distinct personalities—extroverted, introverted, assertive, and passive—for both Nao and Pepper robots. The aim is to embody these traits in their movements, dialogues, and interactions to provide a tangible representation of each personality type.

C. Scenario Creation

Controlled scenarios will be developed where the robots, bearing different personalities, interact with human participants. These scenarios will be carefully crafted to allow robots to display empathetic behaviors influenced by the designed personalities.

D. Participant Interactions

A group of participants will interact with the robots in each of their distinct personalities. After each interaction, participants will be asked to rate their perceptions of the robot's empathy. This will provide a direct assessment of how different personalities influence human perception.

E. Data Collection

A combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection methods will be employed. Qualitative data will be gathered through post-interaction interviews, while quantitative data will be collected through structured surveys. Furthermore, participants' facial expressions, verbal feedback, and body language during interactions will be analyzed to glean deeper insights into their perceptions. In the data collection phase, participants' perceptions of the robot's empathy will be gauged using a modified version of the Robot's Perceived Empathy (RoPE) scale. So participants will rate their perceptions of the robot's empathy in all cases.

F. Data Analysis

Following the data collection phase, the obtained data will be subjected to preliminary analysis. Potential machine learning methods may be explored to derive meaningful patterns and insights, particularly when processing complex datasets

such as facial expressions or verbal feedback. Techniques like neural networks or NLP methods could be particularly useful, though the exact methodologies will be refined as the project progresses.

G. Comparative Analysis

The data collected will be analyzed to compare the perceived empathy across different robot personalities and appearances. This will help in identifying key factors that most significantly influence perceived empathy in human-robot interactions.

V. EXPECTED CONTRIBUTIONS

A. Interdisciplinary Exploration

Our research breaks new ground by examining the nexus of robot personality, appearance, and perceived empathy, an intersection that hasn't been extensively explored. This interdisciplinary approach promises to shed light on how these factors work in tandem.

B. Informed Robotic Design

Our findings will serve as a practical guide for robot designers. By pinpointing the ideal blend of personality traits and appearances that enhance perceived empathy, designers can tailor robots for more effective human-robot interactions.

C. Theoretical Expansion

Beyond its practical implications, this research enriches the academic discourse on human-robot interaction. By elucidating the combined effects of robot personality and appearance, we're advancing theoretical understanding in a rapidly evolving domain.

D. Broad Application Potential

Robots that are perceived as more empathetic can have transformative impacts in real-world scenarios. From healthcare to hospitality, robots crafted with our findings in mind could revolutionize industries by fostering better human-robot relationships.

VI. CONCLUSION

This proposed research aims to delve into uncharted territories of human-robot interaction, specifically focusing on the intertwined dynamics of robot personality, appearance, and perceived empathy. As robots continue to permeate our daily lives, understanding how their design can foster deeper human connections becomes paramount. By exploring how different personality traits and appearances influence a robot's perceived empathy, we hope to uncover insights that will pave the way for more harmonious human-robot coexistence. The expected contributions from this study, both practical and theoretical, underscore its significance in the ever-evolving field of robotics. As we embark on this research journey, our next steps will include refining our methodologies, solidifying experimental scenarios, and setting the stage for data collection. Ultimately, we aim to enrich the broader discourse on empathetic robots and shape the future of their design for the benefit of society.

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